

INFLUENCE OF DIELECTRIC MATRIX ON ELECTROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF MWNT-BASED NANOCOMPOSITES

A.I. Romanenko^{a,c,*}, O.B. Anikeeva^{a,c}, E.N. Tkachev^{a,c}, K.R. Zhdanov^{a,c}, V.L. Kuznetsov^{b,c}, I.N. Mazov^{b,c}, K.V. Elumeeva^{b,c}, S.I. Popkov^d, K.A. Shaykhtudinov^d.

^aNikolaev Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Novosibirsk, Russia; ^bBoreskov Institute of Catalysis, Novosibirsk, Russia; ^cNovosibirsk State University, Novosibirsk, Russia; ^dKirensky Institute of Physics, Krasnoyarsk, Russia.

* Corresponding author(air@niic.nsc.ru);

Abstract

Temperature $\sigma(T)$ and magnetic field $\sigma(B)$ dependences of conductivity of composite materials containing different types CVD multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) in dielectric matrices (polymethylmetacrylate (PMMA), polystyrene (PS), polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE)) have been investigated. Two sets of MWNTs with narrow diameter distribution in the range of 8-10 and 20-22 nm, both pristine and heated in Ar flow at 2200, 2600 and 2800°C were used. High temperature MWNT annealing results in the increase of the contribution of quantum corrections to the normalized conductivity ($\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$). Similar behaviour of conductivity was observed for the composites MWNT/PMMA. At the same time the deviation from dependence typical for quantum corrections to conductivity takes place for composites on the basis of PS, PP and PE using as dielectric matrixes. The difference in the conductivity behaviour of PMMA-based composites on the one hand and composites on the basis of PS, PP and PE on the other hand is explained in terms of different wetting of the CNT surface with these polymers. PS, PP and PE demonstrate very good wetting of MWNTs. That results in limiting contacts between individual MWNTs.

Keywords: *Nanotubes, dielectric matrix, conductivity, magnetoresistivity, quantum correction.*

1 Introduction

Electron transport properties of conducting materials are the basic characteristics determining their application potential. Electron transport properties of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) depend on the electronic state of surface atoms representing an appreciable part of total number of atoms in nanomaterials. Thus, the interfaces between MWNTs and dielectric matrix can be crucial for the design of new tailor-made composite materials with specific electron transport properties. Here, we have studied the temperature $\sigma(T)$ and magnetic field $\sigma(B)$ dependences of conductivity of two sets of as-grown and annealed (2200-2800°C) MWNTs with fixed mean diameters of 8-10 and 20-22 nm as well as composites materials on the basis of MWNTs and polymer dielectric matrices.

2 Experimental

MWNTs of two types with average outer diameters of 8-10 and 20-22nm were produced via

ethylene decomposition at 650–700°C in standard CVD oven setup using Fe-Co catalysts. As-grown MWNTs were first purified by boiling in 15% HCl and then washed with distilled water. Then, dried MWNTs were annealed in resistivity heated graphite oven using high purity argon flow (99.999%) at temperatures 2200, 2600 and 2800°C [1].

The composite materials containing MWNTs obtained were synthesized on the basis of various dielectric matrixes like polymethylmetacrylate (PMMA) [2], polystyrene (PS), polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE).

The structure of MWNTs before and after annealing was investigated using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (Fig. 1). The MWNTs after heating possessed the ppm level of impurities [1]. According to TEM data (Fig. 2 (b, c)) the synthesized samples consist of MWNTs with defective structure and have very low concentration of amorphous carbon. All samples show narrow distributions of average outer diameter of MWNTs mostly depending on the synthesis conditions.

Optical microscopy, scanning and transmission electron microscopy were also applied in order to characterize the homogeneity of MWNT distribution in polymer matrices.

$\sigma(T)$ and $\sigma(B)$ of MWNTs and composite materials on their basis were measured by four point-probe technique. To carry out the electrical measurements of tubes the powder of MWNTs was pressed in a glass cylinder. The electrical contacts were made by 0.1 mm silver wires. $\sigma(T)$ was measured in the temperature range of 4.2–300 K. $\sigma(B)$ was measured in the field B range of 0–9 T. Our previous studies of powder carbon nanostructures carried out by this method showed the stability and reproducibility of electrophysical properties [1-11].

Fig.1: Transmission electron microscopy images of pristine (top) and annealed (bottom) nanotubes.

3 Results

3.1 Conductivity of MWNTs and MWNT-containing composites in different dielectric matrixes

Figure 3 shows the typical curves of temperature dependence of normalized conductivity $\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ (σ_{293} -conductivity at room temperature) of MWNTs with fixed mean diameter $d=20-22$ nm and 8-10 nm. As one can see from Figure 3 the ratio between conductivity at room temperature and conductivity at temperature of liquid helium increases during the heating of samples, and is higher for nanotubes with smaller average diameters. This phenomenon relates to changes in the regular part of conductivity (in temperature interval 50-300 K) as a result of decreases of charge current concentration in MWNTs due to annealing of defects or decreasing of the average outer diameter of MWNTs.

Fig.2: TEM micrographs of MWNTs (top) and histograms of distribution of average outer diameter d of these MWNTs (bottom).

Fig. 4 reveals the dependences of σ at room (300 K) and liquid helium (4.2 K) temperature versus concentration of MWNT in PMMA and polystyrene matrices. Percolation threshold of the electrical conductance for composites lays in the range of MWNTs concentration lower than 0.5 wt.% for MWNT/PMMA (top curves in Fig. 4) and 10 wt. % for MWNT/PS (bottom curves in Fig. 4) materials.

Fig. 5 shows the dependences of $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ for MWNTs with average diameter $d=20-22$ nm and

MWNT/PMMA composite, where σ_{293} is conductivity at room temperature, $\Delta\sigma(T) = \sigma(T)_{\text{exp}} - \sigma(T)_{\text{reg}}$, $\sigma(T)_{\text{exp}}$ is experimental data, and $\sigma(T)_{\text{reg}}$ is regular part of conductivity obtained by extrapolation of $\sigma(T)_{\text{exp}}$ in interval 50-300 K with supposition that it is constant at 4.2 K.

Figure 6 shows the dependences of $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ for MWNTs with average diameter $d=20-22$ nm and MWNT/PS composite. The dependences of $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ for MWNTs with average diameter $d=8-10$ nm and MWNT-containing composite in PMMA, PP, and PE matrices are shown on Figure 7.

Fig.3. Temperature dependences of normalized conductivity $\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ for MWNTs with average outer diameter $d\sim 20-22$ nm (top) and $d\sim 8-10$ nm (bottom): \circ – initial sample; $\color{red}\circ$, $\color{green}\circ$, $\color{blue}\circ$ – after annealing at 2200°C, 2600°C, and 2800°C, correspondingly.

Logarithmical dependences of $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ take place for all samples (see fig. 5) at temperatures below 50 K (Eq (1)):

$$\Delta\sigma(T) = \sigma_1 + A \ln(T), \quad (1)$$

where σ_1 and A are the constants. This dependence is typical for quantum corrections to conductivity in two dimensional conductors with local disorder [12]. The contribution of quantum corrections to normalized conductivity increases after annealing of samples. Logarithmical dependences of $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ take place for initial samples (see figures 6 and 7) at temperatures below 50 K. The deviation from the dependence (1) takes place in MWNT-containing composites with different dielectric matrices.

Fig.4. Dependences of conductivity σ of composite materials versus MWNT concentration in PMMA (top figure) and PS (bottom figure) matrices. \circ - σ at room temperature (300 K), \bullet - σ at temperature of liquid helium (4.2 K)

Fig. 5. Temperature dependences of normalized conductivity $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ in $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293} - \ln(T)$ axes for MWNTs with average outer diameters $d \sim 20-22$ nm (two top curves - \circ and \bullet) and composite in PMMA matrix with MWNT concentration 10 wt.% (two middle curves - \circ and \bullet) and 5 wt.% (two bottom curves - \circ and \bullet). Open points – MWNTs annealed at 2200°C, full points – at 2800°C.

Fig. 6. Temperature dependences of normalized conductivity $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ in $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293} - \ln(T)$ axes for composite in PS matrix with MWNTs concentration: \circ - 100 wt.% (initial sample); \bullet - 40 wt.%; \circ - 30 wt.%; \circ - 20 wt.%.

3.2 Magnetoconductivity of MWNTs and MWNT-containing composites with different dielectric matrices

Magnetic field B suppresses quantum corrections (Eq. 1) to conductivity [13]. The magnetoconductivity in the case of domination of quantum corrections of interaction of electrons to magnetoconductivity $\delta\sigma_{\text{int}}(B)$ shows the asymptotic behaviour at low B [13]:

Fig. 7. Temperature dependences of normalized conductivity $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ in $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293} - \ln(T)$ axes for MWNTs with average outer diameters $d \sim 8-10$ nm (\circ) and composites with PMMA matrix (\circ -5 wt.% of MWNTs, \bullet -2.5 wt.%), with PP matrix (\circ -8 wt.%, \bullet -4 wt.%), with PE matrix (\circ -8 wt.%, \bullet -20 wt.%).

$$\delta\sigma_{\text{int}}(B)/\sigma_0 = -\sigma_2 g(T)(B/B_{\text{int}})^2, \quad B/B_{\text{int}} \ll 1 \quad (2)$$

where σ_0 -conductivity at $B = 0$, σ_2 is constant, $B_{\text{int}} = \pi c T / 2eD \approx 6$ T at $T=4.2$ K, $D \approx 20$ cm^2/s for MWNTs [14] (diffusion coefficient), $g(T)^{-1} = 1/\lambda + \ln(\gamma\eta/\pi k_B T)$ is interaction constant, λ - the constant of electron-electron interaction (at attraction of electrons the temperature of superconducting transition is $T_c = \theta_D \exp(1/\lambda)$), $\eta = E_F$ at repulsion and $\eta = \theta_D$ at attraction of electrons, θ_D/k_B is Debye temperature. As one can see from Eq. (2) the $\delta\sigma_{\text{int}}(B)/\sigma(0) = -\delta\rho_{\text{int}}(B)/\rho(0)$ is positive when $g(T)$ is negative. Fig. 8 shows the magnetic field B dependences of normalized magnetoresistivity $\rho(B)/\rho(0)$, where $\rho(B)=1/\sigma(B)$ is the experimental

results of measurement of magnetoresistivity of MWNTs and MWNT/PMMA composites with MWNT concentration 5 wt.%. We have found that the MWNTs under investigation do not contain the amorphous carbon. Thus, only quantum corrections for interaction electrons to magnetoconductivity [9] $\delta\sigma_{\text{int}}(B)=1/\delta\rho_{\text{int}}(B)$ take place. Fig. 8 (bottom) shows the relative magnetoresistivity of MWNTs in the $\rho(B)/\rho(0) - B^2$ axes. In these axes the $\rho(B)/\rho(0)$ has a parabolic approximation in the magnetic field range of 0-1 T (the straight line on bottom curves in the Fig. 8).

Fig.8. Magnetic field B dependences of normalized magnetoresistivity $\rho(B)/\rho(0)$ ($\rho(0)$ – the magnetoresistivity at $B=0$) of MWNTs (full points) and MWNT/PMMA composites with MWNT concentration 5 wt.% (open points) Two top curves are for MWNTs with average outer diameters $d \sim 8-10$ nm and two bottom curves are for MWNTs with $d \sim 20-22$ nm.

4. Discussion

The logarithmic dependences of $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ indicate that at $T \leq 50$ K two dimensional quantum correction to conductivity take place for as-grown as well as annealed MWNTs with average mean diameters $\bar{d} \sim 8-10$ and 20-22 nm. The contribution of quantum corrections to normalized conductivity $\Delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ increases after thermal annealing of samples. Similar increases take place for MWNT-containing composite in PMMA matrix. The deviation from dependence (1) takes place for MWNT-containing composites with PS, PP and PE dielectric matrices. The increase of slopes for $\delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$ curve for composites demonstrates that interaction of surface atoms of nanotubes with material of dielectric matrixes leads to increase of quantum correction to $\delta\sigma(T)/\sigma_{293}$. These results are in good agreement with data on magnetoresistivity. The decrease of normalized magnetoresistivity $\rho(B)/\rho(0)$ with decreasing concentration of MWNT in composites demonstrates that interaction of dielectric matrix with surface layer of multiwalled carbon nanotubes leads to decrease of quantum corrections contribution for interaction of electrons [12-13] to magnetoresistivity of composites materials.

The difference in the conductivity behaviour of composites on the basis of PMMA on the one hand and composites on the basis of PS, PP and PE on the other hand can be explained in terms of different wetting of the CNT surface with these polymers. HR TEM and SEM data (not presented here) demonstrate that polymer molecules have different ability of wetting MWNT surface. PS shows the best wetting ability of MWNTs in comparison with somewhat less wetting ability of PE and PP. PMMA has the lowest wetting ability among the investigated polymers. High wetting ability of polymers results in limiting contacts between MWNTs which finally influences the composite conductivity.

Acknowledgement

The work was supported by Ministry of Education and Science of Russian Federation (Grant N: PFI.2.1.1/10256); Program No 27 of the Basic Research of Presidium RAS (Grant No. 52); the Russian Foundation of Basic Research (Grant No.

09-02-00331 and 11-03-00351); the state contracts Nos. P339, P898, 16.740.11.0016, 16.740.11.0146, and by the ISTC project B-1708.

References

- [1] V.L. Kuznetsov, K.V. Elumeeva, A.V. Ishchenko, N. Yu. Beylina, A.A. Stepashkin, S.I. Moseenkov, L.M. Plyasova, I.Yu. Molina, A.I. Romanenko, O.B. Anikeeva, E.N. Tkachev "Multi-walled carbon nanotubes with ppm level of impurities" *Physica Status Solidi (b)*, Vol. 247, No. 11-12, pp. 2695-2699, 2010.
- [2] I.N. Mazov, V.L. Kuznetsov, S.I. Moseenkov, A.V. Ishchenko, N.A. Rudina, A.I. Romanenko, T.I. Buryakov, O.B. Anikeeva, J. Macutkevici, D. Seliuta, G. Valusi, J. Banys "Structure and Electrophysical Properties of Multiwalled Carbon Nanotube/Polymethylmethacrylate Composites Prepared via Coagulation Technique" *Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Letters*, Vol. 3, pp. 18–23, 2011.
- [3] V.L. Kuznetsov, Yu.V. Butenko, A.L. Chuvilin, A.I. Romanenko, A.V. Okotrub "Electrical resistivity of graphitized ultra-disperse diamond and onion-like carbon". *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 336, No. 5-6, pp. 397-404, 2001.
- [4] A. I. Romanenko, A. V. Okotrub, V.L. Kuznetsov, A. S. Kotosonov, A. N. Obrastsov "Heterogeneous electronic states in carbon nanostructures with different dimensionalities and curvatures of the constituent graphene layers". *PHYSICS-USPEKHI*, Vol. 48, pp. 958-962, 2005.
- [5] A.I. Romanenko, O.B. Anikeeva, V.L. Kuznetsov, T.I. Buryakov, E.N. Tkachev, S.I. Moseenkov, A. N. Usoltseva "Influence of gases on conductivity of onion-like carbon and multiwalled carbon nanotubes". *Journal of Optoelectronics and Advanced Materials*, Vol. 10, No. 7, pp. 1749-1753, 2008.
- [6] A.I. Romanenko, O.B. Anikeeva, T.I. Buryakov, E.N. Tkachev, K.R. Zhdanov, V.L. Kuznetsov, I.N. Mazov, A.N. Usoltseva "Electrophysical properties of multiwalled carbon nanotubes with various diameters". *Physica Status Solidi (b)*, Vol. 246, Nos. 11-12, pp. 2641-2644, 2009.
- [7] A.I. Romanenko, O.B. Anikeeva, V.L. Kuznetsov, T.I. Buryakov, E.N. Tkachev, S.I. Moseenkov, A. N. Usoltseva "Influence of gases on conductivity of onion-like carbon and multiwalled carbon nanotubes". *Journal of Optoelectronics and Advanced Materials*, Vol. 10, No. 7, pp. 1749-1753, 2008.
- [8] A.I. Romanenko, O.B. Anikeeva, T.I. Buryakov, E.N. Tkachev, K.R. Zhdanov, V.L. Kuznetsov, A.N. Usoltseva, A.V. Ischenko "Influence of curvature of grapheme layers of multi-walled carbon nanotubes on electrical properties" *International Journal of Nanoscience*, Vol. 8, Nos. 1-2, pp. 1–4, 2009.
- [9] A.I. Romanenko, O.B. Anikeeva, V.L. Kuznetsov, T.I. Buryakov, E.N. Tkachev, A.N. Usoltseva "Influence of helium, hydrogen, oxygen, air and methane on conductivity of multiwalled carbon nanotubes_" *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, Vol. 138, No. 2, pp. 350-354, 2007.
- [10] E. N. Tkachev, A. I. Romanenko, O. B. Anikeeva, T. I. Buryakov, V. E. Fedorov, A. S. Nazarov, V. G. Makotchenko, V.L. Kuznetsov, A. N. Usoltseva, *JETP* 105 (2007) 223.
- [11] Z.R. Ismagilov, A.E. Shalagina, O.Yu. Podyacheva, A.V. Ischenko, L.S. Kibis, A.I. Boronin, Y.A. Chesalov, D.I. Kochubey, A.I. Romanenko, O.B. Anikeeva, T.I. Buryakov, E.N. Tkachev "Structure and electrical conductivity of nitrogen-doped carbon nanofibers". *Carbon*, Vol. 47, No. 8, pp. 1922-1929, 2009.
- [12] B. L. Altshuler, A. G. Aronov, P. A. Lee "Interaction effects in disordered Fermi systems in two dimensions" *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 44, No. 19, pp. 1288-1291, 1980.
- [13] B. L. Altshuler, A. G. Aronov, A. I. Larkin, D. E. Khmel'nitskii "Anomalous magnetoresistance in semiconductors" *Sov. Phys. JETP*, Vol. 54, No. 2, pp. 411-419, 1981.
- [14] M. Baxendale, V.Z. Mordkovich, S. Yoshimura, and R.P.H. Chang "Magnetotransport in bundles of intercalated carbon nanotubes", *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol. 56, pp. 2161-2165, 1997.